

Reliability Analysis of a Reinforced Concrete Drainage Structure

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Abstract

A reliability assessment was performed to examine potential modes of unsatisfactory performance for a six-barrel gravity drainage structure and pumping plant located under a 33-ft-high levee section. The structure is composed of reinforced concrete which has suffered severe structural deterioration and exposure of reinforcement. This structure is a critical element in the levee system that protects a major metropolitan area from river and bayou flooding. Loss of this structure during a project flood event would lead to a high probability of loss of life because of its proximity to a highly populated area. Using soil-structure interaction analyses, the outer culvert wall was modeled as a beam-column subjected to lateral and vertical earth pressures, and hydrostatic water pressures. Monte Carlo Simulations and First Order Second Moment techniques were utilized to examine the reliability of the culvert for normal operating conditions and for project floods of fifty and one hundred years.

Introduction

The drainage structure, pumping plant, and levee were constructed in 1935. The existing drainage structure consists of a reinforced concrete box culvert with six openings (two 5 ft, 5 in. x 11 ft, 1 in., two 5 ft, 6 1/2 in. x 11 ft, 1 in., and two 5 ft, 8 in. x 11 ft, 1 in.). The primary function of the structure was to operate as a drainage outlet for the waters of the bayou into the main river. The structure which is 386 ft long and 41 ft wide was built through the levee that protects a major metropolitan area from flooding.

During periods of high water on the river, the six culverts are closed off to river flow by sluice gates located on the riverside of the structure. For periods of high water in the bayou, the middle four sluice gates are opened on both sides and act as gravity fed-drains while the outer two culverts are pumped by two horizontal axial flow pumps. The outer two culvert gates on the bayou side of the structure always remain closed because the pumps feed from the pump house back into the roofs of the outer

culverts. Figure 1 shows a typical cross section of the drainage structure, and Figure 2 shows the existing project plan.

Figure 1 - Typical cross section of drainage structure

The drainage structure and pumping plant have deteriorated greatly primarily due to age and continuous use. The structure has had structural repairs for an outlet erosion problem in 1983, grouting under the outlet slab in 1984, and repairs and replacement to the gate guides in 1988. During the repairs and dewatering in 1988, inspection of the inside of the culverts of the drainage structure was possible.

During this inspection, numerous spalls of concrete and "honeycomb" pockets of exposed reinforcement in the walls of the culvert were discovered. The deterioration of the reinforcement in these exposed areas was so extensive that the reinforcement could be considered completely ineffective. Structural cracks (3/8 in. to 1/2 in.) were found which ran in both the transverse and longitudinal directions of the culvert roof and walls. The extent of the degradation of the reinforced concrete experienced during this inspection led to serious questions regarding the safety and the structural integrity of the project. The ability of the structure to perform satisfactorily during a project flood event of any duration coupled with the fact that the structure is adjacent to a hospital facility and a highly

populated downtown area prompted serious concern regarding the structure.

Figure 2 Existing project plan of drainage structure

Reliability analysis

Deterministic model

The deterministic model developed for the drainage structure has been refined based on the failure and collapse of an exterior wall of the six-barrel culvert structure. The collapse of an exterior wall would allow the levee crown to subside, disrupting the capabilities of the consolidated levee soils and creating a zone where the levee could be breached and flooding could propagate into the downtown area. A failure of the culvert during a flood event, i.e., 50 or 100 year, could cause a large portion of the downtown area to become flooded creating large dollar costs for flood damage, a large population at risk, and potential loss of life if the event were to occur with little or no warning.

The model utilizes the behavior of the exterior culvert wall as a simple reinforced concrete beam which is analyzed for its capacity in both moment and shear. This representative beam segment is subjected to lateral earth pressures, internal water pressures, and axial loads from the soil and concrete above. The various loadings on the beam that are used in the model are shown in Figure 3. Figure 4 shows the beam, its sectional properties, and the resultant trapezoidal loading.

The deterministic model is simplified by the assumption that longitudinal cracks exist in the top corners of the exterior wall of the culvert. These cracks have been verified from inspection of the culvert during low water times prior to the pooling of lock and dam downstream and from the dewatering and inspection of the culverts in 1988. The interior culvert walls were once considered for a performance mode, but since the force from the lateral earth pressures is much greater than internal water

pressures, the exterior walls were considered to be the most crucial elements of the structure.

Figure 3 External loadings on culvert walls

The deterministic model establishes the limit state as a capacity versus demand relationship in both moment and shear using basic reinforced concrete design and analysis procedures for the beam. This equation is simply expressed for either moment or shear as:

$$\text{Limit State} = \frac{\text{Capacity}}{\text{Demand}}$$

Typically, in the design of reinforced concrete, a beam/column is first designed to carry a design moment based on the loads that are applied to the structure. Next, the beam/column is designed to carry the shear from those same applied loads. If the reinforced concrete beam/column is considered to perform unsatisfactorily in moment, the concrete beam/column does not actually collapse, but its moment demand is greater than the moment capacity. The ability of the reinforced concrete beam/column to carry the shear becomes the most crucial factor. If the demand in shear is greater than the capacity of the beam/column, the beam/column will perform unsatisfactorily and the wall will most likely collapse.

Figure 4 Representative beam model

Limit State 1 - Moment

Capacity

The moment capacity of the reinforced concrete beam was determined by using the Corps of Engineer computer program, CASTR [6], which can investigate existing designs of concrete structures in accordance with ACI 318-89 [1]. CASTR outputs the nominal design moment for various axial loads in the form of interaction diagrams. The nominal moment from CASTR was then modified by a strength reduction factor, ϕ , to determine the design strength or capacity of the beam. This relationship is expressed by:

$$\text{Design Strength} \geq \text{Required Strength} \quad \text{or} \quad \phi \cdot M_n \geq M_u$$

The strength reduction factor was determined in accordance with ACI Section 9.3.2.2 for axial load and axial load with flexure. The ACI code allows the ϕ to be increased linearly from 0.70 to 0.90 as ϕP_n decreases from $0.10f_c A_g$ to zero. The mean value for strength reduction factor was determined to be 0.83 based on a mean axial load of 16.2 kips.

The moment capacity for the column utilized for the Monte Carlo simulations was derived from the ACI 318-89 [1] equations to determine ultimate moment for a singly reinforced concrete beam subjected to axial load.

Demand

The moment demand was determined from the output from the Corps of Engineers computer program, CBEAMC [3], which is a one-dimensional finite element beam-column analysis program. CBEAMC has the ability to output the maximum moments and shears and their location as well as moments and shears for each node in the entire beam-column.

The moment demand for the Monte Carlo simulations was determined from the combination of load cases from LRFD beam tables for both a combination of uniform and triangular loading.

Limit State 2 - Shear

Capacity

The shear capacity of the culvert wall was determined by using ACI 318-89 [1] Equation 11-4 for shear with axial compression effects.

Demand

The shear demand was also determined from the output from the Corps of Engineers computer program, CBEAMC [3].

The shear demand for the Monte Carlo simulations was derived from the combination of load cases from LRFD beam tables for both a uniform and triangular loading.

Probabilistic Model

Constants

The constants used in the model reflect values that were deemed capable of being held as a constant with confidence. Primarily, these constants represented the elevations of the levee and structure and the unit weight of water.

1. Elevation of top of levee. The mean profile for the levee was determined from three profiles of the levee recently taken at different stations on the levee above the drainage structure. These stations were Sta. 1254+67.98, Sta. 1253+67.98, and Sta. 1252+67.98. The mean profile showed a mean elevation at the crown at 98 ft. Figure 5 shows the mean profile of the levee.

Figure 5 Mean profile of existing levee

2. Elevations and interior height of culvert. Elevations at the top and bottom of the culvert were 65 ft and 52 ft, respectively. The interior height of the culvert was taken as 133 in. (11 ft 1 in.). The elevations and height of culvert used as constants in the analysis are shown in Figure 6.

3. Unit weight of water A value of 62.4 pcf was used as the constant for the unit weight of water.

Figure 6 Elevations and dimensions of exterior culvert

Variables

The nine variables, their distributions types, and statistical values are discussed below. Each variable has a particular effect on both the capacity and demand side of the limit-state equation. Each variable represents some true variability in the modeling of the drainage structure, and this variability will account for many likely combinations of the differences that are possible.

1. Elevation of water - River side

a. Normal operating. Elevations of the water on the riverside of the drainage structure during normal operating conditions can range from 64 to 67 ft. A uniform distribution with a mean value of 65.5 ft and a standard deviation of 0.866 ft was used in the model.

b. 50 year flood event. Elevations of the water on the riverside on the structure during a 50-year flood event can range from 83.4 to 85.4 ft. A uniform distribution with a mean value of 84.4 ft and a standard deviation of 0.5774 ft was used in the model.

c. 100 year flood event. Elevations of the water on the structure during a 100-year flood event can range from 87.1 to 89.1 ft. A uniform distribution with a mean value of 88.1 ft and a standard deviation of 0.5774 ft was used in the model.

2. Elevation of water - Bayou side

a. Normal operating. Elevations of the water on the bayou side during normal operating conditions can range from 64 to 73 ft. A uniform distribution with a mean

value of 68.5 ft and a standard deviation of 2.598 ft was used in the model.

b. Bayou flood event. A stage flood condition for the bayou was not analyzed for this study since the lowest hydrostatic pressures in the culvert would occur during normal operating events and not during a bayou flood event. A worst case scenario of normal to flood events waters on the river side and normal operating water in the bayou side was utilized for this study.

3. Unit weight of soil. The values for the unit weight of soil in the levee were determined by soil testing from borings in the levee. A normal distribution with a mean unit weight of 120 pcf with a standard deviation of 5 pcf was determined.

4. At-rest earth pressure coefficient. The at-rest earth pressure coefficients were estimated based on research from Brooker and Ireland [2], Mayne, et al [7], and Mesri [8]. To represent the uncertainty expressed in this variable, a distribution was determined to range from 0.5 to 0.9. A uniform distribution was used with a mean of 0.7 and a standard deviation of 0.1155.

5. Width of culvert wall. The original width of the culvert wall was 15 in., but a recent inspection in 1989 showed that the reinforcement in the culvert walls had become exposed and rusted. The 2 in. cover had been eroded off over the past 60 years. To model this loss of width, a uniform distribution with a mean of 14 in. and a standard deviation of 0.5774 in. was utilized.

6. Unit weight of concrete. The values for the unit weight of concrete in the structure were obtained from testing performed during repairs of the outlet slab in 1984. A normal distribution with a mean unit weight of 145 pcf with a standard deviation of 5 pcf was determined.

7. Compressive strength of concrete. The compressive strength of concrete in the structure was determined from testing performed during repairs of the outlet slab in 1984. These values were also confirmed from the specifications for the pumping plant in 1932. A normal distribution with a mean compressive strength of 2,500 psi with a standard deviation of 500 psi was used.

8. Area of reinforcing steel. The area of the reinforcing steel is directly dependent upon the amount of cover that was lost. If the entire 2-in. cover had been removed by erosion and the steel had been exposed, the area of the reinforcing steel would be reduced. If the cover had not

removed, the steel would be intact and the area would still be the original area. In the Monte Carlo simulations, a correlation coefficient of one was used to account for this fact.

a. Not exposed. The area of the reinforcing steel that was not exposed was based on two 7/8 in. bars per foot of wall. This yielded an area for the reinforcing steel of 1.2 in. Since the type of bar was not specified (round or square), a normal distribution of 1.2 in. with a standard deviation of 0.1 in. was used.

b. Exposed. To account for the corrosion of the steel that had been exposed in the structure, the area of the reinforcing steel was assumed to have a normal distribution of 1.1 in. with a standard deviation of 0.1 in. The variation in area may have been much larger, but without actual measurements this range should be sufficient to model loss of area.

9. Yield strength of reinforcing steel. The yield strength of the reinforcing steel was based on knowing that in general two different yield strengths of steel, 36 ksi and 40 ksi, were being used in the field in 1932. Since no information is available from the specifications, a uniform distribution between 36 and 40 ksi was used. The mean value for yield strength of 38 ksi with a standard deviation of 1.15 ksi was used in the analysis.

Reliability Results

First-Order-Second Moment (FOSM) Method

A FOSM Taylor Series Finite Difference (FOSM-TSFD) Method used in this report uses the formulations for reliability expressed in ETL 1110-2-532 [4] as:

$$E[F] \approx F(\mu_i)$$

$$\sigma(F) \approx \sqrt{\sum \left(\frac{F_i^+ - F_i^-}{2} \right)^2}$$

$$\mu_{\ln F} = \ln[E[F]] - \frac{\sigma_{\ln F}^2}{2}$$

$$\sigma_{\ln F} = \sqrt{\ln \left[1 + \left(\frac{\sigma(F)}{E(F)} \right)^2 \right]}$$

$$\beta = \frac{\mu_{\ln F}}{\sigma_{\ln F}}$$

The results showing the reliability and the probability of unsatisfactory performance for the FOSM-TSFD method of analysis for normal operating, a 50-year flood event and a 100-year flood event are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 FOSM-TSFD Results

Limit State 1

<u>Moment</u>	β	<u>R</u>	<u>P(U)</u>
Normal operating	-0.2222	0.4121	0.5879
50 year flood event	-0.3864	0.3496	0.6504
100 Year Flood Event	-0.4503	0.3263	0.6737

Limit State 2

<u>Shear</u>	β	<u>R</u>	<u>P(U)</u>
Normal operating	-0.1814	0.4280	0.5720
50 year flood event	-0.3328	0.3697	0.6303
100 Year Flood Event	-0.3947	0.3465	0.6535

Monte Carlo Simulations

Monte Carlo simulations (MCS) were run for comparison to the FOSM-TSFD method. The results showing the reliability and the probability of unsatisfactory performance values for 20,000 simulations are shown in Table 2. The results from the Monte Carlo simulations used in this report use the formulation for reliability expressed from the guidance for Major Rehabilitation Reports [5] as:

$$\beta = \frac{\ln \left[\frac{E[C]}{E[D]} \right]}{\sqrt{V_C^2 + V_D^2}}$$

Table 2 - Monte Carlo Simulation Results

Limit State 1

<u>Moment</u>	β	<u>R</u>	<u>P(U)</u>
Normal operating	-0.1382	0.4450	0.5550
50 year flood event	-0.3665	0.3570	0.6430
100 Year Flood Event	-0.4584	0.3233	0.6767

Limit State 2

<u>Shear</u>	β	<u>R</u>	<u>P(U)</u>
Normal operating	-0.0893	0.4644	0.5356
50 year flood event	-0.2935	0.3846	0.6154
100 Year Flood Event	-0.3785	0.3525	0.6475

Conclusions

The results from the FOSM-TSFD and MCS indicate a close comparison in the reliability estimation determined by the use both of procedures. The main focus from the results is that both procedures indicate a very low reliability (i.e., negative) for the structure under both normal operating condition and 50- and 100-year flood events. This would seem to indicate though that the exterior walls of the culvert should have already failed and collapsed. However, because the probability of unsatisfactory performance is not near zero, the likelihood of the exterior wall of the culvert still standing is almost as equally likely.

This can be explained by using as an example the moment capacity of the wall under normal operating conditions. The probability of unsatisfactory, $P(U)$, in moment was determined from the analysis to be 0.5879. This number indicates that out of 1,000 walls of similar like and condition, 588 walls should have failed in moment. This leaves 412 similar walls that would not have fail at all in their moment capacity. Hence, the drainage culvert is still standing because it has either not failed in moment (most unlikely scenario), or has failed in moment and not in shear (most likely scenario). This can be directly shown by the joint probabilities for the two failure modes (moment and shear) for each the three operating events (normal operating, 50 year event, and 100 year event). These joint probabilities can be illustrated using the event tree shown in Figure 8.

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Figure 8 Joint probabilities for drainage structure

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